

Synthesis and characterization of Dye sensitized solar cells using natural dye extracted from blue pea flowers

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Abstract

Nanostructured TiO₂ thin films were prepared by spin coating method on fluorine - doped tin oxide (FTO) plate at 6000rpm. The structural characterization done by X-ray diffraction (XRD) reveals the formation of rutile phases of TiO₂. The crystallite size of the sample calculated by Scherrer formula from the full width half maximum of (1 1 0) plane is 21 nm. The natural dye (anthocyanin) was extracted from Blue pea flower by using ethanol and their pH values (3.2, 3.4 and 3.6) were varied by adding 0.1M of HCl. The photoanode required for DSSCs was prepared by sensitizing TiO₂ thin films with these dye solutions. The band gap of the samples calculated from Ultraviolet visible (UV –Vis) and Photoluminescence (PL) techniques are in the range of 2.5 to 2.7 eV. The DSSCs prepared were using these photoanodes were characterized by I-V measurements using Keithely source meter. The DSSC prepared from the dye having pH = 3.2 has shown maximum conversion efficiency of 0.026 %.

Keywords: Natural dyes, Anthocyanin, Photoluminescence, DSSC.